

IMPROVING ENGLISH PRONUNCIATION OF UZBEK LEARNERS WITH ENGLISH SONGS

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Abstract: Some English sounds do not exist in Uzbek, making it difficult for Uzbek pupils to produce English sounds. The findings of the observations revealed that songs are effective aids for improving pronunciation. This article investigates the significance of English songs in incorporating into English classes in order to enhance pronunciation abilities. Previous hypotheses in the field were investigated. Questionnaires and focus group interviews were conducted with English students and EFL teachers at UzSWLU. The findings of the study will be utilized to develop an online social network for interactively teaching English pronunciation.

Keywords: pronunciation, improve, widely spoken, speed, period, available, degree, freelancing

1. Introduction. The English language is one of the most widely spoken worldwide languages. A high degree of ability in this language is critical for keeping up with the speed of this sophisticated period. Because practically all information is available in English. Online courses, high-quality textbooks, YouTube videos, and other learning resources are generally available in English, although they are less likely to be available in other languages. Employees with a high degree of English proficiency are being sought by businesses all around the world. People who know English may find work anywhere, even without leaving their homes, through online freelancing and online teaching. The English language is one of the means by which Uzbek youth, scientists, students, and employers may reach a worldwide audience. Since decades, several projects have been launched in Uzbekistan to broaden the scope of the English language teaching and learning process. In recent years, studying English has begun at a young age for children, with English language being included into kindergarten programs. Furthermore, this learning technique continues throughout the educational system and is regarded as one of the key subjects in school, college, and university curricula. In response to these measures, the great majority of private language centers have opened in locations ranging from central cities to isolated rural areas. Almost everybody who wishes to study English has the opportunity to do so. Furthermore, there are numerous online materials with restricted budgets that language schools cannot access.

The majority of learners in Uzbekistan are either English instructors or students who wish to study abroad, or future scientists who want to go further into their issue and use language as a tool to get more information for their research. As a result, it stands to reason that they will assess their English language abilities using either the CEFR (Common European Framework of Reference for Languages) scale or the IELTS (International English Language Testing System). As a result, in order to pass these assessments, all students must demonstrate competency in four major skills: reading, writing, speaking, and listening. Cambridge and Oxford University textbooks are widely used by teachers to instruct their pupils. English educators employ complex programs that include audio resources, CDs, real materials, and textbooks to teach pupils. Even the most dedicated English learners have difficulties in improving their communication abilities. To begin with, the grammar of the English and Uzbek languages differs significantly. These languages' word formation, sentence structure, and pronunciation have no relation. Another reason students struggle to communicate in English is that they have never encountered a native speaker and their knowledge is limited to textbooks and pointless classroom routines. Another reason they believe they are poor communicators is a lack of English pronunciation abilities. Most pupils are befuddled by English pronunciation restrictions that appear to never stop. In Uzbek, words are pronounced exactly as they are written, however in English, there are more sounds than letters and every word might be spoken in an unexpected way. This is a mind-boggling occurrence for Uzbek students. Learning the words transcribed one by one or learning their pronunciation takes hours and requires a lot of attention from the students. Furthermore, these precise pronunciation standards might be lost in a short amount of time. There are, of course, a plethora of textbooks, online and audio materials, and YouTube videos accessible to teach pronunciation.

Nonetheless, most learners are irritated and confused since they don't know what to study. S.Pd., M.Hum) songs are the ideal resources to employ to improve pronunciation abilities since they are memorable, energetic, and rhythmic. Students can become accustomed to uttering English sounds spontaneously after hearing the songs several times. Popular tunes are also a terrific way to unwind. Another study conducted by Khairi Ikhsan demonstrates that songs are crucial elements for mastering pronunciation. The author contends that pronunciation should be taught in a non-threatening environment, particularly for individuals who have difficulty utilizing the English language using effective ways. Furthermore, songs provide a change in a traditional

English classroom where pupils might become bored with the never-ending regulations of the English language. Songs and their dictation appear more amusing and entertaining to them. Songs naturally and subconsciously teach a large number of supra-segmental (such as rhythm, stress, and intonation in a second language) norms. Songs actually introduce the lowering of specific sounds in speech. They give a direct atmosphere by using native English speakers' pronunciation. They are obviously the finest technique to learn stress and intonation in English since pupils love to sing along with the vocalist and practice the supra-segmental elements instinctively while the song is performed. According to most instructors' experiences, songs may be used as a tool to meet their needs and wants during the learning process. Songs enhance all four needed abilities, including sub-skills like pronunciation. (Ikhsan) FluentU.com is an unusual way to learn English since it uses a natural approach to teaching English skills. It is beneficial for learners to be familiar with both the language and the culture. They give realistic learning resources such as real-life music and films. Along with the real music, they provide a wide range of practicing tasks that are graded based on the students' ability. (Goyo) Esolcourses.com is another website that provides various good tracks that help with pronunciation. The songs are divided into three categories on the website: "easy songs," "medium difficulty," and "Christmas songs." The website provides genuine material and an excellent structure. Each song is taught using a variety of exercises, including multiple choice questions, listening activities, vocabulary review, and other sorts of drilling and practice. (Lyon-Jones) Busyteacher.com is another amazing website that specializes in teaching English pronunciation through songs, where teachers may discover any resources and worksheets to educate their students in any topic. According to Andianto study report (Andianto), not all types of songs are ideal for use in the English classroom. Regardless of the difficulties and prejudices, teachers should add songs that are generally popular among the kids' classmates. Songs, on the other hand, have been shown to lower student attention. In addition, song comprehension is an important factor to consider. It is fine to utilize songs in English classes as long as the lyrics are simple and do not provide any difficulties in understanding. Finally, when choosing the correct tunes, avoid negativity. Positive, lively, energetic, and humorous tunes are not difficult to discover. IKIP Mataram (Ahmad Idris Asmaradhanil and Ruslan Abdul Gani⁴) Although there is no specific obligation to select a certain song, the above- mentioned factors should be examined seriously.

3. Methodology. The relevant data was gathered using both qualitative and quantitative approaches. The suggested research sought to investigate the significance and need of adding songs into the English language. The study's population consisted of intermediate and upper- intermediate level English learners from UzSWLU, as well as English language teachers from all departments at university. The study was done in two parts. To collect qualitative data, the researcher conducted focus group interviews with students of various levels (approximately 40). The interview questions were asked in Uzbek to intermediate students, and the dialogue was held in English to advanced English learners. The researcher either wrote down or recorded the responses during the interviews. To reach a broader range of respondents, interview data were utilized to develop questionnaire questions with numerous alternatives.

Teachers introduce songs into the classroom as a form of entertainment, such as during board meetings or group tasks with a time constraint. According to some responders, teachers share their favorite music with them. Sometimes teachers just utilize the song for motivating purposes. Questionnaires were used to collect data in the second stage. This survey intended to investigate the significance of songs in improving the pronunciation abilities of English learners.

4. Results and Discussions. According to the findings of the study, songs are highly popular among English learners and even professors. There is no one who does not enjoy listening to English music. Thus, introducing English songs into the English classroom would not discourage students from participating in activities. Songs, in reality, motivate learners to study and learn English language more since they have a significant ability to enhance English learners' confidence. The report offers the following based on study findings:

- Rather of utilizing songs in English classes as a time filler when there are no exciting activities to do, generating activities using songs while adhering to certain pronunciation guidelines is significantly more efficient. Creating such activities for songs is not rocket science; rather, it is dependent on one's imagination;

- A selection of popular inspirational songs from today. Students might become bored with old-fashioned or outdated music, however the above-mentioned renowned songs piqued their attention and encouraged them to participate in classroom activities more passionately.

A teacher should also bear in mind that the songs chosen should be culturally suitable, as most English songs include objectionable words. Choosing them would harm the teacher's reputation among pupils;

- The research findings may be utilized to create an online social network and a hard-copy book with songs and related activities to enhance pronunciation.

5. Conclusion. Essentially, students and learners study English in order to communicate in it. However, because English sounds do not exist in Uzbek, most Uzbek speakers fail to pronounce them. The good news is that songs are valuable resources for incorporating into English classrooms and improving students' pronunciation abilities. Because of the rhythmic nature of song lyrics, any student who learns a song by memory will never forget it. Furthermore, songs ensure that students participate in classroom activities. English songs typically contain strong background music that draws students' attention to activities. Students are less likely to be hesitant to participate in significant song-related activities. The songs can help English students in a variety of ways. Further study into using English songs to teach how to pronounce suprasegmental components of the English language can be conducted.

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